

Breaking the Sacred Ceiling: Women's Struggles
for entry into Hindu Religious Spaces.

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Introduction:

Menstruating women are still viewed as “impure” in India, a beautiful and vast country that views all people equally under Article 14 of the Constitution and worships women as goddesses. These women are prohibited from sitting on couches, sleeping on mattresses, cooking, cleaning, performing rituals and practices, and visiting temples because doing so would compromise the “purity” of the temple. Because of how far society has come, it has become “normal” for women to be excluded during their periods, which stigmatizes women’s bodies.

Hindu religious priests attempt to defend their actions by claiming that they must get enough of rest throughout their periods, which prevents them from doing all of these activities. However, since everyone has different needs and preferences, the question that still comes up is: What if a woman wants to pray when she is menstruating? Is she going to be permitted to enter Temples? Will she be permitted to pray? Can she do the rites on her own?

The Menstruating Goddess:

The Maa Kamakhya Temple in Guwahati, Assam, is the first temple that springs to mind while discussing menstruation. The sacrifice made by Goddess Sati to preserve her honour comes to mind when we consider Kamakhya Temple. Sati Learnt that she and her Shiva weren’t invited to a yajna hosted by Daksha, her father while all other Gods and Goddesses were. She was embarrassed by her father when she confronted him and questioned him, and she retaliated through jumping in the yajna kund. Vishnu’s Sudarshana Chakra split the body of Sati into 108 pieces, and the Kamakhya temple is where the Yoni fell.

The mother goddess Kamakhya is represented at this temple as a Yoni (Womb), which is a Vulva or vagina and stands for fertility and the beginning of all life. Additionally, this temple holds an annual fair called the Ambubachi Mela, which takes place in June or July when the Sun enters Mithuna Rashi. The river Brahmaputra, which flows alongside the temple, turns red during the three days of the fair when the Mother Goddess Kamakhya menstruates. The Yoni is dark red in colour, on the fourth day, when the temple’s doors are opened to the public. Tantriks, Shaktas and Aghoris view these three days as crucial since it is the goddess’ divine power, not defilement, that draws them to the temple.

The primary focus of this festival is menstruation, which is viewed as a socially stigmatized topic, making it a very special occasion. Menstruating women are still prohibited from entering many Indian temples, even after a festival of this kind has

taken place in one of the country's most famous temples. How come a regular woman cannot be honoured during her menstruation while a goddess is honoured during the same time?

Andal – The Lover of Sri Ranganathar:

The sole female Alvar Saint in Tamil Nadu is Andal. She was born in SriVilliputhur Town sometime in the ninth or tenth century. According to legend, she was discovered asleep beneath a Tulsi plant as a new-born by Periyalvar, a priest at Sri Ranganathar Temple in Srirangam. He subsequently adopted her as his daughter.

Andal loved Perumal, also known as Vishnu, from a very young age. Her love had grown as she grew older, and poetry was one way she expressed this. During the Tamil month of Margazhi, which falls between December and January, she wrote the Thiruppavai, a collection of thirty verses, each of which is recited daily. Andal urged people to commit themselves to Perumal/Vishnu through Thiruppavai.

She is said to have worn garlands that she had made before presenting them to Sri Ranganathar; a priest discovered this after discovering a woman's hair in the garland. Ultimately, it is stated that Andal became one with her lover, Lord Perumal. She expressed her love for God through her spiritual voice, which was dominated by men at the time. Andal is depicted as a bride who was anticipating her marriage to the lord. This demonstrates that love for God is not limited by religion. If Andal's devotion to God made her a goddess, then why can't regular women express their love for God while they are menstruating?

Every woman should have the same freedom to express her love and devotion to God throughout her life, just as Andal's commitment and love for him granted her a celestial position.

Sabarimala Temple Entry:

In 2018, Sabarimala, a temple devoted to the worship of the Hindu deity Ayyappa/Ayyappan, gained worldwide attention. The temple prohibited women between the ages of 10 and 50 who were menstruating, which sparked prejudice and inequity against women. Ayyappan is a Brahmachari Deity! it was claimed that

Ayyappan's penance would be disrupted if menstrual women were let inside the temple. Given the gravity of the situation, the Honourable Supreme Court of India decided to take matters into its own hands and issued a ruling in 2018 permitting women of all ages to enter the temple.

Although conservative organizations and other segments of society protested the court's decision, which was viewed as a historic step, conflicts between the judiciary and religion resulted. This tension persists because, despite legislative and judicial improvements, women continue to encounter significant resistance and discrimination based on physical impediments.

Conclusion:

In addition to raising concerns about their ability to practice their faith, women's struggles to demonstrate their devotion to God during their periods also reveal how social standards constrain them. When Andal's poetry and spirituality demonstrate her love for God, she can be viewed as a goddess. During the Ambubachi Mela, Maa Kamakhya is regarded as a potent energy source. However, women who are still alive are not allowed to enter temples.